

Report on Training Activities

D2.6

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Executive Summary

EPOS recognizes the importance of training activities to support the new generation of researchers and engineers in facing current challenges in science and IT technology and to promote interdisciplinary collaboration in solid Earth Science and beyond. Thus, training is central in the EPOS communication strategy, whose overarching goal is “to promote understanding for a full and effective exploitation of the EPOS achievements”. Indeed, EPOS IP project has foreseen a specific task (Task 2.4) in WP2 Communication and Dissemination focused on the “Coordination of training activities”. The main aim of Task 2.4 has been to stimulate user engagement through outreach and training activities. Training requires the development and adoption of feasible, shared strategies to engage users and stakeholders; hence, Task 2.4 has worked in close collaboration with WP3, WP6, and WP7 and TCS Communication Contact Persons from all TCS WPs.

Since the beginning of the project (2015) until its end (2019), more than one thousand trainees have been trained in 36 training events focused on: i) training the already engaged users on the potentiality of the EPOS data and services provision and on how to use the new e-platform, ii) training trainers, iii) training for testing and further implement the Integrated Core Service (ICS) platform considering users’ feedbacks and Thematic Core Services (TCS) interactions; iv. educating other stakeholders (private sector and society) about the data and the services accessible through EPOS to transform them into potential new users.

The majority of the training events (86%) have been organised by the EPOS IP Thematic Core Services (TCS) for the training of their respective target audiences (data providers, data users within SES, IT experts, industry and SMEs, higher education and research organisations, including students). In particular the following aspects have been introduced during the trainings’ events: i) main characteristics and capabilities of the services deployed by the TCS; ii) overview of main data products and services by TCSs; iii) use cases on real case scenarios. In addition, feedbacks on the EPOS platform have been conceived as an important insight into user requirements and valuable suggestions for platform improvement and development. These events have also provided the opportunity to strengthen cross-project cooperation’s via representatives’ attendance.

This document describes the EPOS IP training strategy, plan and activities carried out during the entire duration of the project. the document is organised in two sections:

1. EPOS Training Plan;
2. Training Events.

Introduction

EPOS needs to ensure that its achievements are appealing to as many users as possible. This also implies to ensure and reinforce the engagement of data providers and users of the already engaged different thematic community by developing targeted outreach and training activities focused on the provided services. Therefore, EPOS surely needs to instruct the potential, but also the already engaged, stakeholders on how to best exploit data and services provided by diverse scientific communities and on how to utilise the evolving technology for the using and re-using of data. At the same time, EPOS has the ambition to form the next generation of scientists in new ways to face scientific challenges and to develop innovative models and methods to benefit society. The ultimate challenge of the EPOS training programme is to improve the capability of society as a whole to understand the scientific achievements in solid Earth Science and its societal relevance. This will even enable the funding agencies and policy makers to make more informed decisions while understanding, and thus embracing, the scientific and technological advances made possible by EPOS.

The EPOS training activities have been then designed to focus on i) training the already engaged users (e.g. within solid Earth science community, IT expert) on the potentiality of the EPOS data and services provision and on how to use the new e-platform, ii) train trainers, iii) educate potential users (private sector and society) about the data and the services accessible through EPOS.

Thus, the EPOS training plan focused on:

- the exploitation of TCS and ICS services;
- ICS-TCS interoperability, including IT concepts and facilitation of metadata mapping and harvesting;
- Data science and e-science innovation.

The content of the training plan consisted of contributions from EPOS thematic communities (TCS), which were developing training and educational materials and from the IT team to train users and stakeholders on data science and e-science innovation.

The success of the training plan relied on the development and adoption of feasible tools for facilitating training initiatives.

The training strategy has been designed considering the different project' phase. During the first years of the project (2015-2017), when the EPOS service provision was not fully operative, the major efforts were dedicated to the design of the training plan and the development of feasible strategies to engage users and stakeholders, and trainers; while during the remaining period (2018 - 2019), after the service validation process, trainings were focused on: i) acquiring a good knowledge on how to conduct research on the EPOS Platform; ii) hands-on experience on EPOS data and products services; iii) gaining new insights regarding user requirements for platform improvement and development.

1. The EPOS Training Plan

As a key action to accomplish its mission, EPOS is fostering IT innovation allowing the storage, preservation, and curation of large amounts of data integrated from many diverse solid Earth disciplines; this has the ultimate goal of enabling stakeholders from different fields (research, education, society, business) to use, re-use, and exploit data, data products and services for the benefit of science and society. To contribute to this goal, EPOS Training Plan has been designed to be tailored on critical target audiences by focusing on:

1. instructing the already aware/engaged, but also potential, stakeholders on how to best exploit the services provided by diverse scientific communities and utilise the evolving technology for the using and re-using of data;
2. forming the next generation of scientists and at the same time improve the capability of society as a whole to understand the scientific achievements in solid Earth Science and its societal relevance.

1.1 Key Actions

The plan has been structured in “key actions” tailored to specific target audiences (Table 1). All actions are of utmost importance, but they have been accomplished in three phases following an order of relevance in the context of the EPOS IP project and of the Infrastructure and in accordance with the Communication Plan. The content of the Training Plan benefited of contributions from the IT team to train users on data science and e-science innovation and in particular on the exploitation of TCS and ICS services and from each thematic community (TCS) committed to develop training and educational materials dedicated to a more general audience.

Table 1 Key Actions related to the stakeholders, target audiences, content and goal of the EPOS Training Plan.

Phase	Key Action	Stakeholder Category	Target Audience	Content	Goal
First	Training for “aware” users	Scientists	Data providers Data users within SES IT experts	Data and Service Provision; ICS-C	Exploitation of EPOS results
	Training for trainers	Scientists	Data providers Data users within SES	EPOS vision and mission, and provision; Open Science; Open Data	Train next generation of researcher; Inform other stakeholders
Second	Training for potential users	Scientists Society	Data users outside SES Students/Young Researchers	Solid Earth science provision; Open Science; Open Data	Exploit integrated research infrastructures
Third	Training for “specific” users	Governments Private Sector Society	Funding Agencies, Civil Protection Large Industry, SMEs General Public	EPOS vision and mission, and provision	Support decision makers; Engage further users

First Phase

Training for “aware” users

This key action was devoted to train already engaged, therefore fully “aware”, target audiences on how best exploit the EPOS provision. Data Providers and Data Users within solid Earth science (SES) are certainly the EPOS target audiences more advanced in the communication phase. Indeed, they are sharing the EPOS vision and contributing to its mission since the conception phase. Notably, these two target audiences, largely overlap being most of the EPOS data providers also users of the EPOS provision. IT experts are as well aware of EPOS being fully involved in the project since the preparatory phase. Goal of this action was to improve the EPOS User Strategy and to ensure that the EPOS data and services will be fully exploited. Therefore, contents focused on the EPOS data and service provision (DDSS Master Table) and the ICS-C Platform.

Training for trainers

This key action was devoted to train people who covers the role of trainers and/or communicators of EPOS (scientists and in particular to Data Providers). People from this target audience, indeed, contribute to all diverse EPOS thematic core services (TCS) with the data they produce in many different research institutions and, very critical, universities. This action aimed at instructing future trainers from the TCSs community on how to transfer knowledge and capability to potential users within the community itself. Moreover, it was of great importance to provide training in the University context to guarantee the transfer of knowledge to students to form the next generation of scientists. Finally, it was important to train scientists in general, to assure that they have all the instruments and competences to transfers their knowledge to larger audiences. Contents focused on the EPOS vision and mission, and provision; Open Science; Open Data; Solid Earth science.

Second Phase

Training for potential users:

In agreement with its Users Strategy, EPOS foster to engage further users from reservoirs outside the solid Earth science. This training action, on one hand, aimed at disseminating the EPOS vision and mission within other scientific domains; on the other hand, it aimed at initiating, especially the young researchers, to the exploitation of the integrated research infrastructures across Europe. This will allow the next generation of scientists to growth up fully aware of the new available opportunities to access to services from different scientific domains. In turn, this will permit them to develop innovative models and methods fostering scientific excellence to address upcoming scientific challenges. The contents of the training programme focused on the EPOS vision and mission, and provision; Solid Earth science data in general; Open Science; Open Data; European research infrastructure.

Third Phase

Training for “specific” users

Provide training to specific target audience not belonging to the scientific area, e.g. funding agencies, civil protections agencies, private sector, general public, is the most ambitious, and long-term, objective of the EPOS training plan. This action would have a twofold goal of providing to the decision makers up-to-date tools for taking their decision and engage further users. During the EPOS IP lifetime, a baseline for providing such trainings have been conceived and the implementation of this specific sessions will be launched during the EPOS operational phase.

1.2 Training Topics

The EPOS training sessions performed during the EPOS IP project focused on different “Training Topics” that can be summarized as follows:

- EPOS vision, mission, and provision;
- Open Science;
- Open Data;
- Solid Earth science data in general;
- European Research Infrastructures;
- EPOS Data and Service Provision;
- ICS-C Platform.

More in details, specific, technical topics have been the followings:

- Metadata in Geosciences: i.e. Inspire metadata overview, OGC metadata overview, EPOS metadata baseline, EPOS metadata mapping & harvesting workflow, Co-design architecture, Interoperability layer, Harmonization groups training
- Use Cases: i.e. scientists from specific research fields provide an overview of main data products and services and insight on the potentially more interesting integrations with other fields of research (Seismology, including ORFEUS; Near fault observatories; GNSS Data and Products; Volcano Observations; Satellite Data; Geomagnetic Observations; Anthropogenic Hazards; Geological Information and Modeling; Multiscale laboratories; Geo-energy test beds for low carbon energy
- Using the EPOS services: i.e. Graphical User Interface overview, datasets filtering, visualization, advanced integrated visualizations of cross-disciplinary datasets,
- Open-data: i.e. legal and security aspects (AAAI users Authentication, Authorization, Accounting and Infrastructure; EPOS Data Policy).

1.3 Training Methods and Tools

For its training events, EPOS IP project utilised diverse, presently available, communication tools depending on the goal of the event and on the audience needed to be targeted.

The training methods and tools utilized during the training sessions are listed below:

- **Face-to-face meeting.** This is surely the most effective tool to meet stakeholders and it has been used whenever possible.
- **Web meeting and webinar.** These methods represent the most flexible solution to meet stakeholders; they have been organised providing in advance to the participants visual and live audio training materials and they have been conducted showing these visual material on their computer screens. Q & A sessions have been held at the end of sessions.
- **Demonstrations.** Whenever it was possible, at public events, tools presentations and demonstration have been performed by the ICS and TCS teams.
- **User cases.** User cases have been considered an excellent way to have hands on real case scenarios for different stakeholders.
- **Q&A sessions.** Informal question-and-answer sessions have been always handled, followed by a question-and-answer period and a discussion period.

The training section of the EPOS Web site has been developed as a simple and clean repository of reference documents linked from the wiki and video instructions categorized in training tracks (i.e. ordered sequences of lessons concerning a particular subject), with an additional tagging system for cross-references between related modules found in different tracks.

Concerning the video modules, the suite of tools provided by google Hangouts for live-streaming and automatic recordings archived on YouTube, provides all that is needed both for production and massive distribution on all hardware device types or operating systems. A dedicated EPOS training YouTube channel provides the possibilities of managing different tracks (main training subjects), making tracks private or public, integrating them on the EPOS Web site seamlessly. Moreover, interested parties could subscribe to tracks with any rss-feed app and further customize their consumption of EPOS training materials.

The intranet discussion groups (mailing lists) in use on the EPOS intranet, represents both a good distribution platform for the community (training announcements) and a discussion forum as well as a collaborative working environment for those managing the release of the training units.

2. Training Events

The training events described in this paragraph took place from the beginning of the EPOS IP project, December 2015 [M3] until June 2019 [M45]. Target audiences have been the internal and external Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research), data providers, data users, IT experts, industry, NGO. A complete list of all training sessions performed during EPOS IP project is provided in Table 2. The rationale of training activities performed by WPs involved in training events is described in the following.

2.1 Description of the training activities undertaken by WPs (M3-M45)

Training activities organised by WP1 - Management

The EPOS Project Management Office organized two online webinars titled “How to use the EPOS intranet”, aimed to train on how to use the various features of the EPOS intranet. The EPOS intranet (<https://intranet.epos-ip.org>) created at M2 by INGV, ensures daily communication among EPOS community members and, in particular, EPOS IP project partners. The platform includes different tools and features (dedicated work spaces, file sharing/repository, mailing list, event management, web conference, project task management, calendar, wiki), and it is structured in public and private areas. Currently, the intranet counts around 550 users. The first e-training was specifically addressed to WP leaders (n. of participants: 15 people). The second EPOS online webinar was addressed to TCS components (n. of participants: 40 people). The webinars took place at M6 and M7, respectively.

Training activities organised by WP2 – Communication and Dissemination

The WP2 webmaster team, organized on April the 4th 2017, an online webinar that took place on the EPOS intranet training room, titled “How to use Drupal platform”. The goal has been to give information and instructions to the TCS Communication Contact Persons and their proxies on how get access to the Drupal platform and manage the TCS internal web-pages (e.g. add text and pictures, figures). The public website www.epos-ip.org (D2.3) launched at M3, addresses the widest promotion of EPOS initiatives and EPOS IP project goals, vision and objectives. At the end of M18, TCS web presence was improved with the

development of new sections dedicated to the 10 thematic communities ([TCS web pages](#)) likewise reachable through the EPOS IP website home page. Trust-IT implemented this platform extension in collaboration with INGV, whilst content updating is under the concerned TCSs CCP responsibility. After the training session, all participants have been provided with a ppt presentation and a Guideline document.

Training activities jointly organised by WP6 ICS-TCS integrations and interoperability & WP7 ICS Design and development

The WP6 and WP7 have jointly organised training sessions during the last year of the project for testing and further implement the Integrated Core Service (ICS) platform considering users' feedbacks and TCS interactions while the previous years were focused on the system development. Thus, the training sessions aimed at present the technical components of the EPOS architecture to experts, scientists from multiple disciplines to further improve the development work toward the public release of the EPOS Data Portal. These trainings were open also to the participation of externals to EPOS so that they were not biased toward possible IT solutions and the TCS-ICS interaction in the system's background. Feedbacks on the usability of the system (appearance, functionality, performance, bugs, etc.) have been collected by participants for improving the functionality of EPOS Integrated Core Services Central hub, a system for integrate Data, Data Products, Software and Services provided by European data providers in the domain of Solid Earth Sciences.

Training activities organised by WP8 – TCS Seismology

The training workshops organised in WP8 TCS Seismology aimed to inform about EPOS – Seismology in general and discuss on how to exploit its services. A series of "hands-on" sessions have been organised during the ESC week in 2017 and 2018 to provide a live experience how to use the already operational EPOS Seismology services. These workshops gave also the opportunity to engage a broader European seismological community that were not directly involved in the EPOS IP project.

Training activities organised by WP12 - TCS Satellite Data

The WP12 TCS Satellite Data organized several events to present to the scientific community the services planned within the TCS for the exploitation of Earth Observation satellite data resources in the context of the Geohazard Supersites & Natural Laboratories as well as on the CEOS Pilots on Seismic Hazards and Volcanoes. These events included short training courses targeted to introduce the main characteristics and capabilities of the services deployed by the TCS and to engage the solid Earth science (SES) community. The short training courses have been mainly organized within important international conferences, such as EGU General Assemblies and AGU Fall Meetings, where a very large part of the SES community has been easily intercepted. Moreover, the WP12 partners participated to training-days organized by European Universities (ETH Zurich and Harokopio University of Athens) to present to the national communities' new initiatives in the Earth Observation and SES fields.

The training courses were focused on the ESA's Geohazards Exploitation Platform (GEP) and its main benefits for the users. GEP is a collaborative, virtual work environment providing access to EO data and the tools, processors, and Information and Communication Technology resources required to work with them, through one coherent interface. GEP is the gateway of the TCS Satellite Data, and the access point to its services and products. The fundamental principle of the GEP is to move the user to the data and tools. Users access a platform work environment providing the data, tools, and resources required, as opposed to downloading,

replicating, and exploiting data 'at home'. This virtual workplace provides access to: i) EO satellite data; ii) Computing resources and hosted processing; iii) a platform environment, allowing users to run and manage applications and providing access to standard platform services and functions such as collaborative tools, data mining and visualization applications; iv) application repositories or stores providing access to relevant advanced processing applications. The training courses organized by WP12 have been the place to directly interact with the users, collecting feedbacks and inputs from them to both enhance the currently planned services and develop new EO methodologies to be profitably exploited by SES researchers.

Training activities organised by WP14 - TCS Anthropogenic Hazards

The majority of training activities organised by WP14 members were small sized (<20 participant) in-depth workshops aimed at higher education representatives, students and researchers from the solid Earth science (SES) community. The main purpose of the training events was to educate current and emerging potential researchers about anthropogenic hazards and seismicity with state-of-the-art knowledge, tools and data using the IS-EPOS platform (the access gateway for TCS AH). To facilitate this, the EPOS TCS AH community prepared an IS-EPOS Platform training workshop programme and training plan. The IS-EPOS platform is a digital research space providing permanent and reliable access to advanced research infrastructures focusing on anthropogenic hazards (specifically anthropogenic seismicity) from geo-resource exploitation. The platform is available at <https://tcs.ah-epos.eu/> and is designed to ensure freedom for experimentation by providing a virtual laboratory in which the researcher can design their own processing workflows to process data integrated on the Platform. The workshop programme is developed from experience of conducting research with the platform, as well as the uniqueness of the anthropogenic seismicity cases. During the workshops, participants acquired basic knowledge on how to conduct research on the IS-EPOS Platform with science-industry integrated multidisciplinary datasets (termed Episodes) and applications (for data processing, analysis and visualisation). They got acquainted with basic applications as: data upload, catalog export from Matlab format to Excel, filtering with date and magnitude, signal download application, work with the seismogram picking tool on the chosen event signals, as well as the more advanced tools as the time-dependent hazard applications spectral analysis and focal mechanism calculations of anthropogenic events. Overall, the training workshops emphasised workspace functionalities promoting integrated research-industry data knowledge, the use of anthropogenic seismicity data in novel ways, the generation of data products and the platforms social and collaborative working services for research sharing. Approximately 10 IS-EPOS platform focused training workshops have taken place with a total of over 200 SES community stakeholders being trained to use the IS-EPOS platform at varying levels across 7 countries during the course of the EPOS-IP project. Integrating the IS-EPOS platform into university teaching as an educational and effective research resource within the TCS AH partner countries and institutions has contributed to these numbers, e.g. TCS AH leaders IG PAS have delivered workshops within Poland and at TCS AH partnering institutions, alongside other partners also delivering training in their respective countries e.g. UOulu utilised the platform in their Mining geophysics course at Oulu Mining School, CNRS used the platform in their GeoRisk Masters course component on Anthropogenic seismicity at the University of Grenoble, and an IS EPOS platform training workshop for students and young researchers also took place at the Swedish partner institution Lulea University of Technology. Introductions to the platform conducted further afield at USA's Miami University in Ohio, has further stimulated growth in the TCS AH community members and use of the

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online services (supplemented by user guides, platform demo videos and a dedicated YouTube channel). The IS-EPOS Platform has also been used as a teaching tool in an educational project called ERIS – Exploitation of Research Results in School practice - aimed for junior high and high schools, funded with support from the European Commission within the ERASMUS+ Programme. Training events with stakeholders from the private, government and public sector (including representatives from industry and an NGO) have also taken place and include the TCS-AH IS-EPOS platform training workshop at Keele University, the Digital Research Space for Anthropogenic Hazard Studies Conference in Katowice, and the Scientific Workshop held in Pisa with the latter attended by significant representation from the private (industry) and government (ministry/civil protection) stakeholder categories. In addition to gaining feedback on the IS EPOS platform for insights into user requirements and suggestions for platform improvement, the training events organised by TCS AH have enabled important face to face stakeholder engagements that have fostered the development of new ideas for the use of the integrated research infrastructure and strengthened cross-project co-operations and bilateral support initiatives.

Training activities organised by WP16 – TCS Multi-scale laboratories

The Multi-scale Laboratories (MSL) community organized a trans-national access (TNA) tutorial at the EPOS-booth during the EGU General Assembly. The goal of this tutorial was to provide a walkthrough on how to gain access to TCS MSL facilities as part of TNA. Around 15 participants attended this training, which consisted of a PowerPoint presentation with the main focal points and a live-presentation of the TNA application procedure. As a direct result, 4 researchers that were previously unaware of the TNA possibilities within EPOS applied to the MSL TNA and are now participating to the 3rd TNA call.

Table 2. List of training events

WP	Title	Date and place	Key Action	Stakeholder Category	Size of audience
WP1	The EPOS intranet	27/04/2016 - 19/05/2016 Online webinar	Training for aware users	EPOS community	55
WP2	The Drupal platform	04/04/2017 – Online webinar	Training for aware users	EPOS community	15
WP6/ WP7	EPOS-Norway Annual Workshop	23-24/01/2019 - Bergen, Norway	Training for potential users	Scientists	40
WP6/ WP7	EPOS ICS-TCS Workshop - Testing & Preoperational	12-15/02/2019 Bergen, Norway	Training for potential users	Scientists	50
WP6/ WP7	User Feedback Group Workshop	03-05/06/2019 Prague, Czech Republic	Training for potential users	Scientists	29
WP8	GFZ International training course on Seismology	04-29/09/2017 Potsdam, Germany	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	30
WP8	Hands-on session: How to use EMSC's Web Services	25-27/10/2017 Lisbon, Portugal	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	20
WP8	Hands-on session: How to use EMSC's Web Services	02-07/09/2018 Valletta, Malta	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	20
WP12	The SBAS-DInSAR web tool for Earth surface deformation analysis through the ESA GEP	15/12/2015 AGU - San Francisco, USA	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	50
WP12	The SBAS-DInSAR web tool for Earth surface deformation analysis through the ESA GEP	17/12/2015 AGU - San Francisco, USA	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	50
WP12	The SBAS-DInSAR web tool for Earth surface deformation analysis through the ESA GEP	20/04/2016 EGU -Vienna, Austria	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	50
WP12	SARwatch. The Sentinel-1 SBAS web tool for advanced DInSAR analyses through the ESA GEP	5-7/10/2016 Porto, Portugal	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	20
WP12	SBAS-DInSAR processing on the GEP	25/01/2017 Zurich, Switzerland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	170
WP12	GEP: An overview of the SBAS-DInSAR web tools for Earth surf. def. analyses	06/06/2017 Helsinki, Finland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	80

WP	Title	Date and place	Key Action	Stakeholder Category	Size of audience
WP12	Training and hands-on - SBAS-InSAR Sentinel-1 TOPS	31/03/2017 Athens, Greece	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	50
WP12	The SBAS-DInSAR web tool for Earth surface deformation analysis through the ESA GEP	27/04/2017 EGU – Vienna, Austria	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	50
WP12	SBAS DInSAR processing on ESA GEP	01/11/2017 Tenerife, Spain	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers	20
WP14	IS-EPOS Platform Workshop at Digital Research Space for Anthropogenic Hazard Studies Conference	21/11/2015 Katowice, Poland	Training for specific users	Government/private sector/society	37
WP14	Training for students on how to use the IS-EPOS Platform	21/11/2016 Sosnowiec, Poland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	44
WP14	Training for students on how to use the IS-EPOS Platform	02/12/2016 Kraków, Poland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	16
WP14	Training for students on how to use the IS-EPOS Platform	05/12/2016 Luleå, Sweden	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	15
WP14	Introducing the IS-EPOS Platform to students	11/11/2016 Miami, USA	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	3
WP14	IS-EPOS Platform Training	21/11/2016 Katowice, Poland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	37
WP14	IS-EPOS Platform Training for Ph.D. students	12/05/2017 Potsdam, Germany	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	15
WP14	IS-EPOS Platform Training for ERIS (Erasmus+) Teachers	09/04/2018 Warsaw, Poland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	10
WP14	IS-EPOS Platform Training for ERIS (Erasmus+) Teachers	16/04/2018 Krakow, Poland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	20
WP14	IS-EPOS Platform Training for STEM Teachers (Scientix Week)	25/04/2018 Warsaw, Poland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	10
WP14	IS-EPOS Platform Training Workshop	12-13/06/2018 Oulu, Finland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	8

WP	Title	Date and place	Key Action	Stakeholder Category	Size of audience
WP14	Mining geophysics course at Oulu Mining School.	10/12/2018 Oulu, Finland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	20
WP14	Induced seismicity teaching using IS-EPOS Platform at Oulu University	10/11/2018 Oulu, Finland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	7
WP14	Induced Seismicity teaching and TCS-AH platform training for Georisk module MSc students	10/01/2019 Grenobles, France	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	8
WP14	Anthropogenic seismicity IS-EPOS platform workshop	26-27/04/2019 Chęciny, Poland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	20
WP14	Anthropogenic Hazards Scientific workshop	09/05/2019 Pisa, Italy	Training for specific users	Government/private sector/society	20
WP14	IS-EPOS Platform Training Workshop	10/01/2019 Keele, U.K.	Training for specific users	Government/private sector/society	17
WP14	Contemporary Geophysics: Seismology course IG PAS Ph.D. studies	01/06/2019 Warsaw, Poland	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	10
WP16	Tutorial on how to apply for Trans-national access	10/04/2019 EGU - Vienna, Austria	Training for potential users	Scientists/young researchers/students	15

Conclusion

In total, 36 trainings were held attended by more than one thousand representatives of target groups. In common opinion of participants, the workshops were evaluated as important events, being the most important source of information on how to utilize the evolving technology for using and re-using EPOS data and services provided by the diverse scientific communities.

Trainings events opened the opportunity to mentor the next generation of scientists and to enable the development of the future data intensive applications and models necessary to address future challenges in the solid Earth Science. The lectures during the training events were accompanied by active participation of the audience. It was appreciated that all topics were elaborated by outstanding international experts with large experience and expertise what resulted in bringing to the participants the high-quality most recent knowledge, information, know-how, and uses cases from EPOS TCS.